

Language and Culture in English Classrooms: ways of addressing, idioms

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ABSTRACT An idiom is a phrase or a clause whose meaning, mostly, cannot be deduced from the literal definition; it refers instead to a figurative meaning which is well-mastered by the native speakers in one particular culture. The present paper is geared towards exploring English idioms on the basis of a large corpus.

Key words : Our, definition, greetings, idioms, addressing

Definition: Succeed in doing two things at the same time (or fixing two problems with one single action)

Example: "I prefer to go to work by train; by skipping traffic and having some time to read, I kill two birds with one stone."

An idiom is a phrase that, when taken as a whole, has a meaning you wouldn't be able to deduce from the meanings of the individual words. It's essentially the verbal equivalent of using the wrong math formula but still getting the correct answer.

The phrase "kill two birds with one stone" is an example of an idiom. Fluent and native English speakers understand that this doesn't refer to harming birds or using stones, but that someone is completing two tasks at once.

Our deep dive into this topic will define what an idiom is, go over the different types, help you understand how to use them in writing, and give you some examples.

1 Have a light-bulb moment

Definition: Have a sudden moment of inspiration or realization

Example: "Marie had a light-bulb moment when she finally realized what was blocking our messages."

2 Think outside the box

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Definition: Try to solve a problem in an original way; think creatively

Example: "Our product line is getting stale. We need to think outside the box and come up with creative new products."

3 Think on your feet

Definition: Capable of adjusting rapidly to new developments and making quick decisions

Example: "Our new sales rep is able to think on his feet when pitching our products, which is great!"

4 A shot in the dark

Definition: Provide an answer or come up with a solution that is a complete guess (that could potentially be close to the truth)

Example: "Our last campaign was just a shot in the dark, I can't believe it turned out so well."

5 Do the trick

Definition: Do exactly what is needed; achieve the desired effect

Example: "Waiting around and hoping for the best won't do the trick. We need to take action."

6 Don't cry over spilled milk

Definition: There is no use in being upset over situations that have already happened and cannot be changed.

Example: "I know we messed up, but let's not cry over spilled milk, and let's see how we can do better next time."

7 To be on the ball

Definition: To be aware of what is happening and able to deal with things quickly and smartly.

Example: "She's the best person for the role; she's always on the ball."

8 Kill two birds with one stone

Addressing Friends and Family Members

When speaking with your friends or family members, you can typically use informal greetings.

Nicknames and terms of endearment are often used as a sign of affection. Of course, the terms you use will depend on the relationship you have with the

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person.

There are certain situations where formal terms are still used with family members. For example, “sir” and “ma’am” are often used by young children when they address their parents, especially in the American South.

Also, if you’re introduced to your friend’s parents, you should use formal greetings until they specially mention that informal greetings are fine.

In both of these situations, formal greetings are used in informal settings as a sign of respect.

Greetings to Know

Honey — An informal greeting used by adults to address children or as a pet name used in a romantic relationship.

Sweetie — Another informal greeting used by adults to address children or as a pet name used in a romantic relationship.

Baby — This informal greeting is most commonly used in romantic relationships, but it can also be used by adults to address children.

Buddy — Typically used to refer to a male friend, child or even a pet.

Hun — Typically used to refer to a female friend or child. However, it can also be used to refer to your romantic partner.

Sir — A formal term for an adult male that often follows “yes” or “no.”

For example: “Would you like a glass of water?”

“Yes, sir, thank you!”

Ma’am — A formal term for an adult female that often follows “yes” or “no.”

For example: “Did you have a good day?”

“Yes, ma’am, how about you?”

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